

Human Resource Management BB-2208

Case Study Analysis: Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad with the Standard Causal

Model of HRM

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Abstract

Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad is a private limited company and one of the few companies in Brunei to specialize in shrimp farming. The key issue that the company has is that the company is not prepared to handle any shrimp based epidemic that could affect them. To apply the company's key issue into the Standard Causal Model of HRM, the company does not have a proper HR strategy to effectively handle any shrimp based epidemic which causes the company to have poor HR practice. The poor HR practice will cause a poor HR outcome where the employees do not know what to do during a shrimp based epidemic which will cause poor internal and financial performance. There are two solutions to solve the company's key issue, first is the "Hire Qualify People " solution which focuses on hiring applicants with the needed qualification and the second is the "Train The Worker" solution which focuses on training the employees to have the needed qualification. It is recommended for the company to either pick or focus mostly on the "Train The Worker" solution. The reason why the "Train The Worker" solution is recommended is because it is more reliable to use when it comes to solving the company's key issue.

Problem Statement

Before we identify the key issues of Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad, we first need to explain what the company is and what do the company do. According to the book of inspiring agripreneurs of Brunei done by Musa ei al. (2020), Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad is a private limited company and one of the few companies in Brunei to specialize in shrimp farming. The company joined the local aquaculture in 1994 and officially began operations in March in the following year. The company is currently being managed by Ampuan Ammilee Farahiyah who is the daughter of the company's founder. The mission of the company is to supply quality organic rostris blue shrimp that are devoid of pesticides and antibiotics while also being disease free. The vision of the company is to be the leading shrimp farm in Brunei and a globally recognized enterprise.

The key issue of Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad can be identify when the company was hit with the White Spot Virus in 2010. The White Spot Virus has almost financially cripple the company where the virus forced to company to destroy the infected shrimp that were harvested from all 22 of the company's pond. The company had to completely rebuild their farm from the ground up after this incident. Based on the info given by Musa ei al. (2020), the company was not prepared to handle the White Spot Virus where they do not have the protocol and the knowledge needed to help the company negated the White Spot Virus on their shrimp. The fact that the company was not prepared to handle the White Spot Virus or any other form of disease related outbreak was further supported when Amouan Ammilee has taken several

measurements to ensure that the company would be well prepared for another outbreak after the White Spot Virus's incident. The measurement ranges from installing various security protocols such as staff training, chlorine baths and quarantine units to educating herself on various shrimp related diseases and how to protect the shrimp farm from it. Therefore, the first key issue of Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad is that the company is not prepared to handle any shrimp based epidemic that could affect them.

Case Analysis

The case analysis will be using the Standard Causal Model of HRM to analyze the two key issues of Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad. The standard causal model of HRM portrays a causal chain that has the beginning stage as business procedure and closure, through the HR forms, with an improved budgetary exhibition (peopleHum, n.d). Figure 1 below describes and shows how HR activities that are aligned with the organization's strategy can lead to a better business performance (peopleHum, n.d). Thus, the HR strategy derived from the overall strategy of the organization so that there is a maximum financial performance (peopleHum, n.d). HR practices such as hiring, training, appraisal and compensation came after HR strategy (peopleHum, n.d). These HR practices can result in HR outcomes like commitment, quality output and engagement (peopleHum, n.d). These HR outcomes will then lead in to improved internal performance such as productivity, innovation and quality (peopleHum, n.d). Once there the improved performance, there be the improved financial performance like increase in profit, financial turnover, better margin and return of investment (peopleHum, n.d). The model also reveals two interesting relationships which are the unmediated HRM effect and the reversed causality. The unmediated HRM effect shows that some HR practices can directly lead to the improved internal performance. For example, having good training can directly result in better performance without influencing the HR outcomes. For the reversed causality, it shows that an improved financial performance can lead to more HR practices and better HR outcomes where the employees are more engaged in the business.

Figure 1: The Standard Causal Model of HRM

To apply the Standard Causal Model of HRM into Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad's key issue, we will label the key issue of the company is not prepared to handle any shrimp based epidemic that could affect them as the overall strategy to effectively handle any shrimp based epidemic. Based on the model to identify the key issue, the company does not have a proper HR strategy aligned with the overall strategy to effectively handle a shrimp based epidemic which will result in poor HR practices for the company to use on their employees. Due to having poor HR practices, it will cause the company to have poor HR outcomes where their employees do not know what to do during a shrimp based epidemic. The poor HR outcome will then negatively affect the internal performance where the productivity and the quality output of the company decrease due to the shrimp being infected by the shrimp based epidemic. Since the internal performance was negatively affected, it will also negatively affect the financial performance where the company almost got financially cripple due to the shrimp being infected and needed to completely rebuild their farm for the ground up afterward.

Alternative Solutions

To create a solution to solve the key issue that Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad has, the solution must have an overall strategy, HR strategy and HR practices which are based on the Standard Causal Model of HRM. For the key issue of the company not being prepared to handle any shrimp based epidemic that could affect the company, the overall strategy for the solution would be to effectively handle a shrimp based epidemic. The solution HR strategy must align with the overall strategy and have HR practices that will help achieve the HR strategy.

Solution #1: "Hire Qualify People"

The "Hire Qualify People " solution is where the HR strategy focuses on hiring applicants who have the experience, knowledge and skill needed to achieve the Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad 's overall strategy to effectively handle any shrimp based epidemic that could affect the company. The reason why this solution was suggested is because the current employees of the company do not have the needed experience, knowledge and skill to handle any shrimp based epidemic. This is supported during the White Spot Virus's outbreak where the company is forced to destroy the infected shrimp that were harvested from all their 22 ponds and almost got the company financially cripple. Thus, this solution will help the company get employees with the needed experience, knowledge and skill by getting applicants with those needed qualities. This solution requires the HR practices of recruitment and selection in order to achieve the overall strategy. The main benefit of this solution is that the company will have access to a large pool of potential

applicants who are qualified to handle a shrimp based epidemic while also help reduce spending money to train their employees with the needed skill and knowledge.

Unfortunately, there are two problems when using this solution to overcome the first key issue that Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad is facing. The first problem is that it will take time and money for the company to find the right applicant. Since companies are looking for applicants who have the needed experience, knowledge and skill to handle any shrimp based epidemic, it would take more time and money for the company to find the right applicant. The second problem is related to the selection process of the company. The way that the company selects the right applicant is heavily affected by the way the company measures the applicant's qualification like their experience, knowledge and skill. The problem with this is that if the way the company measures the applicant's qualification is done poorly, the company has a higher chance to select an unqualified applicant that can't handle a shrimp based opportunity. Because of this, the company needs to also spend time and money to make sure that the selection is reliable for the company to use.

Solution #2: "Train The Worker"

The "Train The Worker" solution is where the HR strategy focuses on training the employees of the company to have the experience, knowledge and skill needed to achieve the Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad's overall strategy to effectively handle any shrimp based epidemic that could affect the company. The reason for this solution is similar to the reason that the first solution uses where the current employees of the company do not have the needed experience, knowledge and skill to handle any shrimp based epidemic. Unlike the first's solution who focus on getting applicants with the needed qualification, this solution focuses on training the current employees so that they could handle any shrimp based epidemic that could affect the company. This solution requires the HR practices of training and development in order to achieve the company's overall strategy. The benefit that this solution gives is that it could improve the employee's performance during a shrimp based epidemic which will also improve the company productivity and the quality of shrimp during those epidemics.

Despite the benefit that the "Train The Worker" solution gives, there are two problems when using this solution. The first problem can be explained by Grugulis (2017) who states that training and development does not occur in a vacuum but as an aspect of an organization's activities and exists to support other activities. With that explanation, the training and development that the Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad made must relate to the company's activities completely or else the employee would not be able to use what they learn during training when they go back to work. The company will have to spend money making sure

the training and development can be used by the employees for the shrimp base epidemic. The second problem is also explained by Grugulis (2017) who state that the employees will feel pressure from the company to perform better once they complete the training. In the company case, the employees will be pressured by the company to perform better during a shrimp based epidemic which can potentially affect their performance.

Recommendations

There are two recommendations that Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad should do to solve their key issue of the company not being prepared to handle any shrimp based epidemic that could affect them. The first recommendations are to pick the “Train The Worker” solution while the second recommendation is to pick both solutions but focus more on the “Train The Worker” solution. The reason why the “Train The Worker” solution is recommended to either be picked or focus on is because compared to the “Hire Qualify People ” solution, it is more reliable to use when it comes to solving the company’s key issue. If the company uses the “Hire Qualify People ” solution, it would take several weeks to several months for the company to find and select the applicant who has the needed experience, knowledge and skill. This solution also does not fully guarantee that the company will find the right applicant in their first attempt which will cause the company to spend more on recruitment. With the “Train The Worker” solution, it is a guarantee that the employees will have the experience, knowledge and skill needed to handle a shrimp based epidemic once they complete their training.

If the company picks either the first or second recommendation, there are three on the job training method and one off the job training method that is based on Raheja (2015)’s journal where the company can use it to train their employees. Under the on the job method, the company employees who are inexperienced in handling any shrimp based epidemic will learn the needed qualification by observing and imitating their peer or manager. These methods do not cost much money to spend and are easier to conduct since they often take place during working hours. The first on the job method is coaching which is a one to one training where it can help identify the company employees’ weakness and focus on improving it. The second on the job method is mentoring which is also a one to one training but it focuses on developing company employees with the needed skill and it uses an employee who knows how to handle a shrimp based epidemic to be the mentor. The third and last on the job method is job instructional techniques. Job instructional techniques is a step by step structure on the job training method where the trainer that the company selected is expected to do four tasks. The first task is that the trainer must prepare a trainee with an overview of the job, its purpose and the desired result. The second task is that the trainer needs to demonstrate the task and the skill that is needed to handle a shrimp base epidemic to the trainee. The third

task for the trainer is to let the trainee do the demonstration that was shown to them on their own. The last task is that the trainer needs to do a follow up on the trainee's demonstration where the trainer is expected to give feedback and help to them. For off the job training, the training is expected to be conducted in an area that is separate from the work environment in the company. The company is expected to provide supply study material and focus on teaching the employee with the knowledge and skill that they needed. The off the job training method that the company should use is the vestibule training. In vestibule training that the company picks, the employees are trained in a prototype environment that is in a working condition related to a shrimp base epidemic. Once the employees are trained in that condition, they should be able to handle an actual shrimp based epidemic when doing work.

For the recruitment and selection process if the second recommendation was picked, the company is expected to put minimum effort on those two processes since the training and development need to be focused on by the company. There are two recruitment methods that were based on Hurrell and Scholarios (2017)'s which the company can use. The first recruitment method is agencies and headhunters, where the company will use agencies and headhunters to find potential applications with the needed quality. Once they find the potential applicant, they will call them in to tempt them to apply to Usaha Asilati Sendirian Berhad. The second method is e-recruitment where the company will use their website or portal as the recruitment channels that host job vacancies and post the information about the job. For the selection process, the company is advised to use a mixed approach of the three selection methods that was based on Scholarios (2017)'s statement to select the right applicant. The first selection method is based on cognitive where the company should use psychometric tests that are designed to measure the applicant's knowledge and skill related to the shrimp base epidemic. The second selection method is based on non-cognitive where the company will focus on the applicant's biographical information to see if the applicant has past experience and work history that is related to the shrimp based epidemic. The third selection method is a performance-based test where it focuses on the applicant's behavior when performing a task during a shrimp based epidemic. In this third selection method, the company should test the applicant's actual performance with a simulation of handling the task during a shrimp based epidemic and their judgment based on the possible behavioral response that they selected to answer the question related to the shrimp based epidemic to measure how the applicant will handle that situation.

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